

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF CONDUCTING PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS CLASSES

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlarini o'tkazishning innovatsion usullari tahlil qilinadi. Jismoniy tarbiya darslarida ishlatiladigan innovatsion texnologiyalarning xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Jismoniy tarbiya mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etishning ba'zi an'anaviy va noan'anaviy innovatsion usullari keltirilgan. Innovatsiyaning pedagogik jihati va uning jismoniy tarbiya mashg'ulotlarini o'tkazishning innovatsion usullarini joriy etishdagi ahamiyati ochib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: innovatsion usullar, jismoniy tarbiya, jismoniy tarbiya, mashg'ulotlar, talabalar.

Аннотация. В статье анализируются инновационные методы проведения занятий по физической культуре и спорту. Рассматриваются особенности инновационных технологий, используемых на занятиях по физической культуре. Приводятся некоторые традиционные и нетрадиционные инновационные методы организации занятий физической культурой. Выявляется педагогический аспект инновационной деятельности и его значимость во внедрении инновационных методов проведения занятий по физической культуре.

Ключевые слова: инновационные методы, физическая культура, физическое воспитание, занятия, обучающиеся.

Abstract. The article analyzes innovative methods of conducting physical culture classes. The features of innovative technologies are considered, physical education classes are used. Some traditional and non-traditional innovative methods of organizing physical culture lessons are presented. The pedagogical aspect of innovative activity and its significance in the implementation of innovative methods of conducting physical culture lessons are revealed.

Key words: innovative methods, physical culture, physical education, classes, students.

The modern educational system requires the development of communicative, cognitive and personal activity of students in dynamically changing conditions of educational activity [1].

Training is associated with a high degree of mental intensity and a significant amount of academic work, while the educational process is characterized by a pronounced intensity, which tends to increase, which is associated with a permanent increase in the flow of scientific information and the need to assimilate them in a short time. This situation has a negative impact on the health of students, which makes it relevant to introduce innovative teaching methods and modernize approaches to physical education, allowing not only to encourage students to independent sports and educational and cognitive activities, but also to correct their mental state by removing the accumulated stress during the school day.

The purpose of the article is to consider innovative methods of conducting physical education classes. To achieve this goal, we used structural-functional and system methods, analysis and synthesis of scientific publications and literature on the topic.

Innovative development of education requires the creation of new pedagogical technologies based on modern approaches to learning and taking into account the features of physical culture as an educational discipline [2]. When developing innovative methods, it is necessary to take into account all components of the educational and pedagogical process: health-improving and pedagogical tasks, training and development orientation, personal and collective approaches, standardized, project-based or creative way of organizing, basic, additional and variable sports.

Partial innovations focused on one or several elements of the educational process will not bring the expected effect, since only complex educational innovations that provide for the implementation of the basic conditions for the formation of educational activities are significant in achieving the result. An important principle in the development of innovative methods is its focus on the widest possible subjects of research, such as physical development, mental and physical health, performance, endurance, the content of sports motives and interests, the level of physical culture and valeological knowledge and the entire lifestyle.

Traditional innovative technologies used in physical education classes are health-saving technologies that provide for the following provisions [3]:

- dosage of physical activities, taking into account the group of health and physical development of students;

- use of special sets of exercises aimed at prevention and correction of vision and posture;
- using a technique that involves alternating periods of relaxation and intensity in the classroom;
- implementation of strict control over the ventilation and temperature regime of the gym;
- conducting inspections and monitoring the condition of sports equipment and equipment, carrying out their timely repair and replacement;
- control over changing shoes and sports uniforms;
- performing regular wet cleaning of the gym.

However, traditional methods of organizing physical education do not provide for the possibility of a proper degree of development of a personal approach required in the context of preserving and improving the health of individuals of the younger generation [4]. The following sports can be used as non-traditional innovative methods of conducting classes:

Yoga. The practice of this system includes methods of physical relaxation and muscle tension techniques that are based on concepts such as relaxation, stretching, accelerated blood circulation, deep breathing, and concentration. The asanas that make up yoga contribute to the improvement of physical strength and flexibility and have a relaxing effect. Yoga can be combined with other physical exercises and is applicable for students who are part of a special medical group.

Nordic walking. It is a highly effective type of physical activity that involves the use of a certain walking technique and exercise techniques using special sticks. It engages and develops about 90 % of all muscle groups, supports the body's muscle tone, reduces pressure on the spine and joints, promotes the dynamic work of the lungs and heart, improves the sense of balance and is a good method of correcting posture. A separate advantage of Nordic walking is the ability to practice it anywhere and at any level of physical fitness.

Stretching exercises. Their base is static stretching of the muscles and joint-ligamentous apparatus, which allows you to prevent and correct postural disorders. Stretching increases joint mobility, muscle elasticity, and improves blood circulation [5].

Step aerobics. It is a type of aerobics in which the movements performed on the stepper are performed by maximum tension of the leg muscles, rather than the back muscles. Regular classes in the form of dance movements help prevent arthritis and

osteoporosis, recover from knee and joint injuries, and improve mental health.

Pilates. It includes a series of exercises that help increase flexibility, restore physical fitness, improve posture, develop and strengthen muscles, and improve coordination.

The use of various innovative methods of physical education contributes to a significant improvement in the indicators of physical fitness and health of students, as well as increases their level of motivation for physical education [6].

Despite the importance of using innovative methods in physical development and the educational process, in practice teachers are not always ready to introduce new technologies. This is associated with the following factors [7]:

- the presence in the teaching environment of a strong belief about the sufficiency of good subject preparation and the desire for qualified transfer of educational information to students for successful teaching;
- teachers do not recognize the need to improve or change the established approach to work due to confidence in their own professionalism;
- low motivation of teachers to participate in development programs.

Effective implementation of innovative educational technologies in physical education classes is impossible without a sufficient level of development of the following criteria of pedagogical readiness [8]:

Coaching staff. It consists in the ability to demonstrate the motor stability and variability of the technique of the chosen sport and perform motor exercises of an increased level of complexity.

Reflexive-pedagogical approach. It consists in the ability to study and analyze best practices in the field of physical culture and effectively solve current pedagogical problems within educational institutions

Recreational and creative. It is a skill of creative organization of recreational work, taking into account the age, gender and individual personal characteristics of students.

Successful implementation of innovative methods in physical education classes is impossible without improving the level of professional competencies of a physical education teacher, which requires the use of appropriate innovative technologies. This makes it important to use innovative methods at all levels of education.

To improve the quality of physical education, it is necessary to actively introduce innovative educational technologies. Increasing the scale of innovative activities in an educational institution, involving more students in classes using the latest technologies,

creating a favorable infrastructure in places reserved for the experimental use of innovative methods and technologies for improving health, humanistic education and organizing students' leisure activities that involve the humanization of sports and its integration with art, contribute to the formation of students' research skills in independent sports and work in physical education classes and improve the quality and effectiveness of physical education.

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